

Data Needs in the Great Lakes

Workshop Summary | April 2021

About this report

This report summarizes the group discussions and priorities that emerged from a workshop hosted by the Gordon Foundation, the University of Waterloo's Water Institute and the Lake Futures project. The workshop was held virtually in December 2020 and the accompanying publication was released in April 2021. Its purpose was to define what is needed to improve access to water quality data in the Great Lakes region.

Suggested citation

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Workshop Hosts

The Gordon Foundation is a 55-year old charitable organization with a long history of protecting Canada's waters and promoting citizen engagement in policy making and action. For the past seven years, the Foundation's Water Program has focused on improving access to water data across the country and on empowering communities to engage in evidence-based decision-making processes. The Foundation's work in this area led to the development of DataStream, an independent, open access platform for sharing water quality data. [Learn more.](#)

The **Water Institute** was established by the University of Waterloo in 2009 to be a global leader in interdisciplinary water research and education. The Institute facilitates interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange in addressing complex water challenges, and promotes innovation in interdisciplinary research and education. With over 170 faculty members, including more than 20 Canada and University Research Chairs, representing 23 departments and schools across all 6 faculties, the Water Institute is the largest research center on campus and the largest water research center in Canada. [Learn more.](#)

Lake Futures is a 7-year research initiative funded through Global Water Futures. The project aims to identify adaptive watershed and lake management solutions that minimize trade-offs between lake ecosystems, water uses, and economic growth. The project, which began in 2017, focuses on issues of eutrophication, nuisance and harmful algal blooms in the Great Lakes. Principal Investigator: Nandita Basu. [Learn more.](#)

Workshop Overview

On December 2 and 3, 2020, 39 participants attended the “Data Needs in the Great Lakes” workshop, hosted by The [Gordon Foundation](#), the University of Waterloo’s [Water Institute](#) and [Lake Futures](#).

The purpose of this workshop was to define what is needed to improve access to water quality data in the Great Lakes region. To do this, the workshop was designed to characterize the current data landscape, identify barriers and opportunities and to work across sectors and communities to brainstorm actions that can improve access to Great Lakes water quality data.

Given the complexity and breadth of data access challenges in the region, the workshop was narrowly scoped to focus on **surface water quality data in the Ontario portion of the Great Lakes watershed**.

This workshop was timely. Among other reasons, it took place as The Gordon Foundation was beginning to build a Great Lakes DataStream hub (slated to be released in the Fall of 2021). This open access platform for sharing water quality data has been operating elsewhere in Canada since 2016 and discussions from this workshop will inform its rollout and growth in the Great Lakes. More information on DataStream can be found here: <https://greatlakesdatastream.ca>.

The workshop took place over four hours, split evenly across two days. Each day opened with a panel of experts. On Day 1, they discussed data challenges and opportunities and on Day 2, the conversation focused on current efforts to address the data challenges in Ontario. The panels were followed by breakout groups that allowed all attendees to share their perspectives on current priorities for making data systematically more available and identified tangible next steps. The Gordon Foundation’s Carolyn DuBois also presented on Day 2 to give attendees a sneak peek at what to expect when Great Lakes DataStream is released in fall 2021.

A total of 39 invite-only attendees represented a diversity of sectors interested in Great Lakes water quality data including federal and provincial governments, Indigenous, academic, environmental non-for-profits and binational organizations. Attendees were chosen based on their expertise in Great Lakes issues and data management.

The purpose of this report is to summarize the workshop discussion and outline options for moving forward. Attendees felt the workshop was critical in raising important issues around data access in the Great Lakes region and ongoing discussion will be needed to maintain momentum towards solutions.

Workshop Objectives

- Discuss the current situation when it comes to accessing water quality data in the Canadian portion of the Great Lakes region. What are the barriers and opportunities to improving data access?
- Discuss initiatives underway that are trying to improve data accessibility and explore ways to leverage and complement this work.
- Introduce Great Lakes DataStream and how it will contribute to data accessibility in the region.
- In addition to existing initiatives and Great Lakes DataStream, discuss what else is needed to improve information flow in the region (e.g., funding, leadership, education, incentives, etc.).
- Determine actions and next steps to build and maintain momentum towards making further progress.

WORKSHOP SCOPE

To promote focused discussion and tangible solution development, we narrowed the content of the workshop to the following criteria:

- The Great Lakes basin in Ontario
- Publicly funded data
- Ambient surface water quality data collected from water bodies. This includes a wide range of physical, chemical and biological characteristics collected within lakes and throughout watersheds. The following will not be the focus for this discussion: water flow, groundwater, fish data, data collected by utilities as part of the water treatment process, satellite data or modelled data.

Workshop Content

This section outlines the main concepts and ideas highlighted by the panelists and/or participants.

Data challenges and impacts across sectors

We asked representatives from a variety of sectors and communities (i.e., academic, non-profit, Indigenous) to share barriers to data sharing and the consequences of a system where data is not easily discoverable or accessible. Here are some highlights from that conversation:

Challenges

- Signing one-off data sharing agreements can be costly in terms of time and resources and they are not always transferable across research teams. However, participants also noted that they can also be beneficial in terms of clearly setting out principles and guidelines for sharing, and creating relationships and commitment to flow and mobility.
- A lot of data is not online and therefore hard to discover/access (e.g., datasets that are only available in hard copy, on floppy disks, or on bookshelves of retired professionals, etc.).
- Insufficient resources are allocated to data management (e.g., for performing Quality Assurance/Quality Control) within many organizations and this hinders data sharing.
- A barrier to making data accessible is the fear that sharing will lead to misinterpretation or misunderstanding by the public.

Impacts of data access issues

- Some researchers end up spending more than 50% of their time looking for and trying to gain access to datasets, leaving less time for analysis and interpretation.
- Limited access to certain types of data, such as recreational beach data, can have human health implications. Data can also lose value when it is not shared in a timely manner. In these cases, investments in data collection are not achieving maximum value-for-money.
- Data deficiencies can severely limit our understanding of the health of our freshwater ecosystems. Even in the Great Lakes (one of the most populated watersheds in Canada), there are areas that lack basic monitoring data.

- For Indigenous communities, lack of access to data from their territories can limit their ability to identify and manage risks to the community. For example, water quality researchers on Six Nations were denied access to arsenic data on their reserve because of a potential risk to property value.
- Even if an Indigenous community can install monitoring sensors on their reserve (and maintain control over this data), they cannot adequately get a holistic picture unless they gain access to comparable data across the whole watershed. This requires collaboration with municipalities and others and such relationships do not always exist.

Progress: Slowly but Surely

A summary of current water quality data initiatives in Ontario's Great Lakes watershed

During the workshop, we asked some of the biggest players in Ontario's Great Lakes data to update us on their data-related objectives and initiatives. What we heard across the board was a strong commitment to actively improving data accessibility and availability despite a number of pervasive barriers and challenges. Progress is happening - slowly but surely.

At the federal level, Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC), which is primarily responsible for water quality data, has an [Open Government data portal](#) with more than 80,000 open data and information assets. They are also currently developing a data strategy for the proposed Canada Water Agency (CWA). Water quality data is one of four types of data they are focusing on. They are beginning with an inventory to locate all relevant data across federal ministries and determine its level of operability. They have also hired consultants to help find data housed by other governments and groups (i.e., private and non-profit sectors, Indigenous, provincial and territorial governments, etc.). Moving forward, they will evaluate existing Information Management and Information Technology (IMIT) infrastructure and propose improvements. Early in 2021, ECCC will host a series of workshops on the CWA, including one specific to data, to engage a wider audience in these conversations.

At the provincial level, the Ministry of Environment, Conservation and Parks leads the data management efforts for water quality data. They have created the [Ontario Data Catalogue](#) that houses over 2,700 datasets, a number that is steadily increasing. You can download data directly from over 800 of those datasets, while the rest point you to the authoritative source of the data. Ontario is committed to making data available where possible and operates under the Open Data Directive and the International Open Data Charter. They abide by a number of principles including making data open by default, ensuring it is comparable and interoperable, and providing opportunity for improved governance, citizen engagement and innovation. The province is working to enhance usability of the data through tools such as interactive maps, story maps and dashboards. They are also looking to improve the way they promote the catalogue and make sure people know what is available.

For **Conservation Authorities (CAs)**, progress is certainly being made toward open data - albeit slowly. There are 36 individual conservation authorities across the province, each responsible for their own water quality data collection and management. A great deal of variability exists between CAs with respect to capacity. The availability of resources (both human and financial) varies from CA to CA, which makes implementation of open data a challenge for some.

Conservation Ontario (CO), the umbrella organization that works for and in support of CAs, is undertaking data management-related initiatives to support information sharing. As part of CO's Information Management Strategy, a user needs assessment and data inventory were recently conducted. This identified over 1,300 CA datasets including drinking water source protection, natural heritage, surface water monitoring, etc. Though some of these datasets were shared and/or openly available many are not due to various perceived barriers including legal/liability issues and data readiness. These initiatives have allowed Conservation Ontario to work with the CAs to develop a list of priority datasets and identify ways to overcome barriers to sharing them. While some barriers to sharing have since been addressed, there is still more work to do.

Another Conservation Ontario initiative to support CAs is the development of a [common metadata application](#). So far, 28 CAs have uploaded information about their discoverable datasets to the app. In addition, some CAs have their own open data sites and CO has an [Open Data Hub](#) where users can find over 214 open datasets. Moving forward, CO remains committed to helping CAs improve the discoverability and accessibility of the data they collect and manage.

In the academic sector, we heard from a representative of [Global Water Futures](#) (GWF), a multi-university, 7-year long pan-Canadian water research project. Individual universities as well as some of the large, well-funded projects have capacity to work towards improved data discoverability and accessibility goals but progress is generally slow. For example, the initial GWF data policy reflected many ideal data practices and set ambitious goals related to the creation, storage, accessibility and sharing of data. When looking to operationalize the policy, gaps in the technical infrastructure and barriers within academia posed serious challenges to progress. As a result, GWF revised its policy to be more flexible. They tailored the policy to account for technical needs and capacity, and to reflect the concerns and state of readiness of researchers and the academic community as a whole. The focus of [the new policy](#) is on data accessibility and GWF data managers are working to support this through the development of a metadata catalogue to act as a data inventory. They are also using existing Research Data Management (RDM) infrastructure such as [Portage DMP Assistant](#), Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR) and Dataverse.

GWF's approach involves both top-down strategies (e.g., program-wide policy) and bottom-up strategies (e.g., providing capacity to support the data management activities of students and faculty as well as offering educational webinars and workshops). It is important to recognize that opening academic-generated data requires a cultural shift. The "publish or perish" environment of academia can promote a strong tendency towards territorialism. It is promising that at a higher level, the Tri-Council agencies, as a major source of academic funding, are currently finalizing a new [Research Data Management Policy](#). This policy, as presented in draft, calls for publicly funded research data to be made accessible and metadata publicly available. The draft policy defines expectations for researchers (i.e. requirements for data management plans and data deposition) and institutions (i.e. recognition of data as research output and various aspects of support of data management excellence) which should help kick start a shift in the culture.

Another ongoing initiative related to Great Lakes water quality data is the [Smart Great Lakes Initiative](#). This binational effort is supported by the [Great Lakes Observing System](#) and aims to build an information ecosystem based on smart technologies that will improve our understanding, use, conservation and management of the Great Lakes. The Initiative is about advancing data management and analysis across the region by leveraging technology innovations that provide high-value information. This is a collaborative effort with many different organizations from Canada and the U.S. involved. They are currently working to develop a framework and common technology platform. In terms of data management, the U.S. is generally more advanced than Canada despite the number of ongoing initiatives (i.e., those described above). So as data on the Canadian side becomes more discoverable and accessible, the Smart Great Lakes Initiative hopes to help ensure that data is synced to binational conversations about policy goals, standards and protocols to facilitate not just a better response to core challenges in the Great Lakes watershed but also facilitate more proactive decision-making.

In addition, [Great Lakes DataStream](#) will be coming online in the fall of 2021. DataStream is an open data platform that brings water quality monitoring results together in one place, in a consistent format – making it easier to share and access data, and connect results in meaningful ways. Great Lakes DataStream builds on the successful regional data hub model implemented with [Mackenzie DataStream](#), [Atlantic DataStream](#) and most recently [Lake Winnipeg DataStream](#). To date, over 100 different monitoring organizations - from community-based monitoring groups to academics and governments at all levels -- are using the platform to publish monitoring results.

Free and open for anyone to use, DataStream is built to support FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles through key features such as the use of widely adopted (meta)data standards (including compatibility with the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) /United States Geological Survey (USGS) developed the Water Quality Exchange (WQX) schema for the exchange of water quality data used by the US Water Quality Portal), interoperability with other systems like Google dataset search and the Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR), dataset version control and DOIs, among others.

Ways to move forward:

Recommendations and Next Steps

The following ideas or concepts were raised during the workshop as suggestions for how we might move beyond a conversation about challenges and opportunities towards action.

Institutional data policies

- Where feasible, organizations should create open data policies that state their commitment to open access and promote a culture shift towards data sharing. In many instances, this commitment can be “baked” into organizational mandates (such as with Conservation Authorities). While such policies are already in place in many organizations that produce and publish data, participants emphasized that they should be complemented with a bottom-up education-based strategy with resources that support implementation of good data management and open data practices.
- Funding (particularly public funding) with data management and data sharing or deposition requirements can be an effective incentive for making data openly available. Resources must be provided to support this activity throughout the research data lifecycle. Open data sharing practices within academia would be further supported by giving researchers credit for the data they create, specifically ensuring that data publications are fully considered in tenure and promotion processes. The Tri-Council Research Data Policy will hopefully work to harmonize funder, institution, and researcher goals and resources to benefit Canada’s academic research output.
- With respect to binational agreements like the Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement and the Canada-Ontario Agreement, more explicit commitments around data would create more formality and a framework for collaboration.

Indigenous data access and data sovereignty

- Indigenous governments and organizations need access to data that is collected by public agencies and others performing water monitoring and research within their regions. Indigenous governments and organizations also run their own monitoring and research and need resources to ensure they can manage and share this information in ways that respect their data sovereignty (i.e., control over their own data). Water data should enable a comprehensive understanding of water from the tap, to source water, to the Grand River to Lake Erie.
- Participants suggested that the new Canada Water Agency could provide the framework and supporting resources to advance data access and sovereignty for Indigenous peoples. The Agency could also ensure that the data will not only be curated but also presented in a format that helps the public understand trends in water and the environment.

- New or strengthened relationships between First Nations and Conservation Authorities could drive better data collection, sharing and use.

Open access culture shift: Education and awareness

- While a culture shift towards data openness is already underway, more work is needed to communicate the benefits and impact of open data and to normalize data sharing. Wherever possible, making data open is the simplest solution for improving access and sharing (i.e., open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike).
- Storytelling can be a powerful communicate tool to illustrate how critical it is to have data that can support informed decision-making. These stories can help people understand the value of open environmental data and foster willingness to support related efforts. Education and storytelling can also help address concerns about risk and liability, for example by talking about how other jurisdictions have opened data successfully and with positive impact.
- It is important to promote open datasets and their potential to support positive outcomes. Data owners should also make a concerted effort to promote the datasets that they have made available and support feedback loops between data producers and end users.

Resources and Capacity

- Data management is resource intensive. Participants emphasized the importance of bottom-up data management: the ongoing, tough work to promote a culture of open data within organizations and hard work by those tasked with data management/curation, including working one-on-one with data producers. As such, a commitment to open data requires long-term investments in personnel and resources to support data management practices (e.g., uploading/digitizing datasets, creating metadata, curating data, monitoring and enforcement of open data policies, standardizing legacy datasets, etc.) as well as education and training to improve data literacy for both data producers and end users.
- Organizations with less capacity and fewer resources can be supported through the provision of services, tools or infrastructure to facilitate open data sharing. This also includes citizen science and community-based water monitoring groups so that their efforts and data can fill data gaps and inform water stewardship and management.

Collaboration: Making data open and accessible is a “team sport”

- With many diverse actors involved in water monitoring, coordination of efforts to improve access to data can provide shared benefits and optimize returns on the time and resources invested by all parties. There is a recognized need for greater collaboration across all sectors from the grassroots through to senior levels of government.
- Adoption of (and guidance surrounding) common data standards enable interoperability and enhance the potential for effective collaboration. Participants emphasized the value of harmonizing water data within Ontario and between the US and Canada, including through the use of consistent data standards that facilitate data sharing, comparability and use.
- Publicly available digital infrastructure for sharing and accessing data in harmonized formats can further improve data discoverability, access and use.

Technical solutions

- Effective, sustainable, easy-to-use technical solutions and platforms are critical in supporting data discoverability and accessibility. Interoperability among complementary systems can support robust digital infrastructure for data sharing, preservation and analysis.
- Understanding the core functionality of different platforms--i.e. whether they catalogue, store/preserve, stream, and/or interpret data (and what type of data) -- is essential to understanding how various platforms can connect and complement one another. For example, it will be important to be deliberate in making connections between the upcoming Great Lakes DataStream and other initiatives including the Great Lakes Observing System, Smart Great Lakes, Water Rangers and the Council of the Great Lakes region (among others).

Next steps

Great Lakes DataStream

DataStream is working with Conservation Ontario, Water Rangers, and others to bring water quality data onto the open access platform in advance of the release of Great Lakes DataStream in fall 2021. As of February 2021, over 6 million water quality observations were uploaded to Great Lakes DataStream. These datasets are stored in a format that is harmonized with data in the US Water Quality Portal.

University of Waterloo/Water Institute

The University of Waterloo's Water Institute is committed to advancing open data goals and supporting a culture shift towards data sharing within academia and beyond. The Water Institute will continue to facilitate dialogue and conversation that brings together researchers, students and stakeholders to address data sharing barriers. The Water Institute will continue participating in efforts such as the Smart Great Lakes Initiative that help innovate open data practices. Finally, the Institute supports researchers by helping them identify appropriate platforms for their data, including Great Lakes DataStream.

Lake Futures

The Lake Futures research team remains highly supportive of open data initiatives. They are committed to sharing all relevant data and findings from the project with Great Lakes DataStream and other platforms, where appropriate. The team continues to work with open datasets to offer interpretive value that improves understanding of water quality trends and identifies viable management options moving forward. Lake Futures continues to facilitate dialogue and conversation that brings together researchers and stakeholders to address data sharing barriers. This includes continued participation in efforts such as the Smart Great Lakes Initiative that help to innovate open data practices.

Canada Water Agency

The Government of Canada is creating a new Canada Water Agency to work together with the provinces, territories, Indigenous communities, local authorities, scientists and others to find the best ways to keep water safe, clean and well-managed. Data has been a key topic in Canada Water Agency engagement sessions and the discussion paper, [Toward the Creation of a Canada Water Agency](#). There is also talk of a data inventory being undertaken by ECCC, which would be an important step towards improving the accessibility of datasets collected with public funds.

Convening

There was consensus among participants that there is value in ongoing convenings that help advance access to water data in the Great Lakes region, and that opportunities for doing so across sectors have been limited to date. In particular, ideas for future discussions include desired features and functionality in data tools and repositories, strategies for addressing barriers to data sharing, ways for data managers to collaborate across sectors, data analysis/interpretation, and data policy implementation.

Appendix

Meeting Agendas

Day 1 - December 2, 10:00 am to 12:00 pm

TIME	AGENDA ITEM	PRESENTER
10:00 - 10:15	Introductions and meeting objectives	Nancy Goucher , Knowledge Mobilization Specialist, University of Waterloo
Part A: Set the stage - What are the data challenges and opportunities with respect to water quality data access in Ontario		
10:15 - 11:00	<p>Moderator: Kelli Paige, Chief Executive Officer, Great Lakes Observing System (GLOS)</p> <p>Panel discussion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquiring data for academic research - Professor Nandita Basu, University of Waterloo • Accessing, interpreting and communicating data for the public - Gabrielle Parent-Doliner, Board Member, Great Lakes Beach Association • Accessing data to assess watershed health - Elizabeth Hendriks, Vice President, Restoration and Regeneration, WWF-Canada • Data needs and initiatives underway in First Nations communities - Professor Dawn Martin-Hill, McMaster University 	
11:00 - 11:10	Break	
11:10 - 11:50	Part B: Improving Ontario's Data Ecosystem Breakout groups to discuss how to make data systematically more available	
11:50-12:00	Wrap up and sneak peek into Day 2	Nancy Goucher , Knowledge Mobilization Specialist, University of Waterloo

Day 2 - December 3, 10:00 am to 12:00 pm

TIME	AGENDA ITEM	PRESENTER
10:00 - 10:10	Day 1 review Objectives for Day 2	Nancy Goucher , Knowledge Mobilization Specialist, University of Waterloo
Part C: Landscape review - Current efforts to address the data challenges in Ontario		
10:10 - 11:00	<p>Moderator: Kat Kavanagh, Executive Director, Water Rangers</p> <p>Panel discussion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal government efforts to promote open data access - Jamie Smith, Chief Data and Results Officer, Environment and Climate Change Canada • Provincial government efforts to promote open data access - Jennifer Winter, Manager, Water Monitoring Section, Ministry of the Environment, Conservation & Parks • Conservation Ontario's efforts to promote open data access - Rick Wilson, Information Management Coordinator, Conservation Ontario • Efforts to promote open data access in the research community - Krysha Dukacz, Data Manager, McMaster University • Smart Great Lakes Initiative - Mark Fisher, President and CEO, Council of Great Lakes Region 	
11:00 - 11:10	Break	
Part D: Great Lakes DataStream		
11:10 - 11:30	Introducing Great Lakes DataStream: Improving access to water quality data	Carolyn DuBois , Executive Director, Water Program, The Gordon Foundation
11:30 - 11:55	Breakout groups to discuss next steps towards building and maintaining progress	
11:55 - 12:00	Wrap up	Nancy Goucher , Knowledge Mobilization Specialist, University of Waterloo

Presenter Information

Nandita Basu, Associate Professor, Water Sustainability and Ecohydrology

Nandita Basu is an Assistant Professor in the [Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering](#) at the University of Waterloo and is also affiliated with the [American Geophysical Union](#).

Her research interests mainly revolve around the sustainable management of water resources. Professor Basu is specifically interested in the study of watershed biogeochemistry under climate and land-use change, and observing its linkages with system sustainability and resilience. Other research interests of Professor Basu's include understanding fate and transport of nutrients and emerging contaminants in human-dominated landscapes, along with catchment travel-time distributions and their role in predicting water quality across scales. She is also interested in modelling hydrology and water quality in depressional landscapes, and studying the sustainability of water resources.

Carolyn DuBois, Executive Director, Water Program, The Gordon Foundation

Carolyn is the Executive Director of the Water Program at The Gordon Foundation where she works with partners across sectors in Canada. This work focuses on improving freshwater stewardship through citizen engagement in decision-making and the use of the best available evidence. Carolyn is a passionate advocate for open data and has led the development of DataStream, an online system that provides access to information about water quality.

Carolyn holds a BSc in Biology from Mount Allison University and a Master's in Environmental Management from the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona.

Krysha Dukacz, Data Manager, McMaster University

Krysha holds a B.A. (hons) in Geography, a GIS Specialist certificate and an MBA (Management of Information Systems). She has worked in the public sector at the federal level (Environment Canada – NHRC) and municipal level (City of Ottawa, City of Saskatoon) as well as in the private and academic sectors. As the Data Manager at McMaster University, Krysha will work with GWF researchers to develop and implement effective data management procedures. In her spare time, Krysha enjoys hiking, skiing, escape rooms and travelling.

Mark Fisher, President and CEO, Council of the Great Lakes Region

Mark Fisher became the President and CEO of the Council of the Great Lakes Region (CGLR) in 2014.

Prior to joining CGLR, he served as a foreign policy advisor in the Privy Council Office, which supports the Prime Minister of Canada and the federal Cabinet, where he focused on advancing Canada's interests in North America and the Asia-Pacific region.

Mark has extensive experience advising senior decision-makers on a range of socioeconomic and environmental issues facing government, business, and the non-profit sector. In addition to CGLR, he is an elected school board trustee with the Ottawa-Carleton District School Board, is a member of the International Joint Commission's Great Lakes Water Quality Board, and is a director on the board of Easter Seals Ontario.

Mark is also a recipient of the Royal Canadian Legion Cadel Medal of Excellence.

Nancy Goucher, Knowledge Mobilization Specialist, University of Waterloo

Nancy is the Knowledge Mobilization Specialist at the University of Waterloo's Water Institute. In her role, she ensures the water research produced at the university is actively used and impacts the way communities and governments prepare for and manage increasing water-related threats. She brings an extensive network and her experience with policy decision-making to this position.

Over the past ten years, Nancy has played an important role in shaping water policy conversations across Canada and particularly in the Great Lakes region. She has experience with a wide array of water issues including algal blooms, invasive species, drinking water and agricultural policy. Nancy has helped successfully negotiate policies including the Canada-Ontario Lake Erie Action Plan, the Great Lakes Protection Act and the ban on plastic microbeads.

Nancy has previously held positions at Freshwater Future, Environmental Defence and the Forum for Leadership on Water (FLOW). She graduated from the University of Waterloo with a Master's degree in Planning in 2007.

Elizabeth Hendriks, Vice President - Restoration and Regeneration, World Wildlife Fund-Canada

With a lengthy background in water policy, Elizabeth leads WWF-Canada's Freshwater team to reverse the decline of freshwater ecosystems across the country through policy, technology and community building. Elizabeth has considerable experience working internationally and nationally on water policy and leads the release of the national assessment of the health and stressors to Canada's freshwater. Elizabeth holds a BA in International Development from Dalhousie University and a MES from the University of Waterloo.

Kat Kavanagh, Executive Director, Water Rangers

Kat Kavanagh is the Executive Director of Water Rangers, an organization aiming to build tools to make it easy for anyone to collect and view water quality data. Kat has 15 years of design and tech experience, plus a Master's degree in Integrated Water Resource Management.

Dawn Martin-Hill, Associate Professor, Department of Anthropology and Indigenous Studies Program, McMaster University

Dawn Martin-Hill (Mohawk, Wolf Clan) holds a PhD in Cultural Anthropology and is one of the original founders of the Indigenous Studies Program at McMaster University. She is the recipient of a US-Canada Fulbright award, Outstanding Teaching Award from the Aboriginal Institutes Consortium, and she has received grants from SSHRC, CIHR and the Ontario Trillium Foundation. Her research includes: Indigenous knowledge & cultural conservation, Indigenous women, traditional medicine and health and the contemporary practice of Indigenous traditionalism. She is Co-PI on a CIHR-IAPH funded NEAHR grant (Network Environments in Aboriginal Health Research), the Indigenous Health Research Development Program (IHDRP).

She currently holds a SSHRC grant for “Preserving Haudenosaunee language and ceremonies through the digitization and translation of the Hewitt Collection” with community partner Six Nations Polytechnic. She resides at Six Nations of the Grand River.

Kelli Paige, Chief Executive Officer, Great Lakes Observing System (GLOS)

Kelli is the Chief Executive Officer of the Great Lakes Observing System (GLOS), appointed as Executive Director in 2015. She has held several positions with GLOS since first joining the organization in 2009 including working with stakeholders, managing product development, and providing strategic direction for the data management and observing projects funded by GLOS.

Kelli came to GLOS from The Nature Conservancy where she served as a Program Coordinator with the Ohio Chapter. She has also worked for the Washtenaw County Drain Commissioner and the Friends of the Chicago River. Kelli holds a BA in Public Policy from DePaul University and a MS in Resource Ecology and Management from the University of Michigan's School of Natural Resources and Environment.

Gabrielle Parent-Doliner, Board Member, Great Lakes Beach Association

Gabrielle Parent-Doliner has been on the board of the Great Lakes Beach Association since 2017. Most recently she was Director of the Swimmable Waters Programs with Swim Drink Fish, directing Blue Flag, citizen science monitoring programming, and Swim Guide. She is recognized for her expertise in recreational water quality data and citizen science, and is the author of the first open data standard for the automated exchange of recreational water quality data. Gabi is from Welland, ON.

Jamie Smith, Chief Data and Results Officer, Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC)

Mr. Jamie Smith began as Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC) Chief Data and Results Officer on July 6, 2020, and assumes the lead to develop a data strategy to support the Canada Water Agency.

Mr. Smith comes from a strong background in data management and collaboration both within and outside Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC). Mr. Smith graduated with his Masters in Geography, Climatology/Hydrology, from the University of Waterloo in 1990 and shortly after joined Environment Canada in the Meteorological Service of Canada (MSC) as an Impacts Climatologist. After further graduate work, Mr. Smith returned to the federal government in a research arm of the Privy Council Office (PCO) researching environmental issues to support policy development. Through his work at PCO on the development of a federal sustainable development strategy, Mr. Smith was recruited to the Treasury Board Secretariat (TBS) to work on the development of the first inter-departmental reporting accountability framework for climate change. Mr. Smith returned to ECCC as the Departmental Assistant in the Minister of the Environment's Office, managing the office staff but also as the liaison with the Deputy Ministers' office and department. Mr. Smith returned to his roots in the Meteorological Service of Canada in 2008 as the Senior Advisor to the Assistant Deputy Minister of the MSC. Following a number of years supporting the ADM and his office, Mr. Smith moved back into the program working as a manager working on water and climate services, monitoring network planning, and partnering with Provinces and Territories to integrate their data into our data management system. Finally, Mr. Smith was appointed as the Director of Monitoring Strategies and Data Services in 2017 responsible for real-time weather and climate archive, earth observations, climate services, and directorate operations and planning.

Rick Wilson, Information Management Coordinator, Conservation Ontario

Rick Wilson has been in the business of conservation for 20 years (he started very young).

In 2013, after 13 years of service with Toronto and Region Conservation Authority, Rick joined Conservation Ontario (CO) as the Water Resources Information Program Coordinator. In 2015 he became Information Management (IM) Coordinator and developed CO's first Information Management Strategy – with a strong emphasis on building capacity to support conservation authorities in moving toward open data. Rick is a strong supporter of the Conservation Authority IM community and of the spirit of collaboration that permeates it.

Jennifer Winter, Manager, Water Monitoring Section, Ontario Ministry of the Environment, Conservation and Parks

Ph.D. Department of Biology, University of Waterloo
M.Sc. Pollution and Environmental Control, University of Manchester (England)
B.Sc. Environmental Biology, University of Liverpool (England)

Dr. Winter currently manages a water monitoring and science team at the Ontario Ministry of the Environment Conservation and Parks whose focus includes the Great Lakes, streams and groundwater. She is an adjunct professor at Trent University and University of Waterloo.

List of Workshop Participants

Last Name	Position	Affiliation
Basu, Nandita	Associate Professor, Water Sustainability and Ecohydrology	University of Waterloo
Boehme, Jennifer	Science Advisor, Board Member	International Joint Commission
Burrows, Mark	Project Manager, Great Lakes Regional Office	International Joint Commission
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